

Nature of Binding in Heavy Metal Halide Molecules

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The molecular spectroscopic constants for heavy metal halides are calculated using the interaction potential energy function in which the coulomb interaction is balanced by the short-range repulsive interaction. We consider two short-range repulsive interactions, viz. Hellmann potential form and a new potential form recently suggested by us. Our calculations are also made by taking into account the contributions of effective charge parameter in coulomb interaction. The results obtained from the new interaction potential is in better agreement with the experimental values than those obtained from Hellmann potential. The present investigation also provides a theoretical basis for the presence of ionic as well as polarised covalent bonding in diatomic heavy metal halide molecules.

THE interaction potential energy functions are simple functions based on the classical electrostatic treatment of interionic interactions and consequently they are regarded as the algebraic sum of various interaction terms. In the present study, we consider only two types of interionic forces, viz. an attractive force of electrostatic origin and the repulsive forces in order to describe the equilibrium of the system. The repulsive forces oppose the mutual overlapping between two electronic clouds associated with the closed-shell configurations of two ions and arise in part from the Pauli exclusion principle.

Varshni and Shukla¹ were pioneer to apply this type of potential energy (P.E.) function to obtain P.E. curves for diatomic molecules. Jain *et al.*² modified the classical P.E. functions by introducing the concept of effective charge parameter in the coulomb interaction. This parameter approximately accounts for the polarisation and covalent effects^{3,4}.

In the case of a diatomic heavy metal halide molecule, one electron from metal atom (M) transfers to the halogen atom (X) and the resulting positive (M⁺) and negative (X⁻) ions attract each other. Hence, heavy metal halides are considered as ionic and are composed of closed-shell configurations. This is why we apply the interaction potential energy functions^{5,6} for these molecules to evaluate their molecular properties which have not been reported so far. These molecular properties include binding energy (D_0), rotation-vibration coupling constant (α_e) and vibrational anharmonicity constant ($w_e x_e$).

Theoretical :

Within the framework of effective charge modes, P.E. functions may be written as

$$U(r) = -\frac{Z^2 e^2}{r} + \frac{A}{r} \exp(-\lambda r) \quad (\text{Hellmann}) \quad (1)$$

$$U(r) = -\frac{Z^2 e^2}{r} + \frac{P}{r^m} \exp(-b r^N) \quad (\text{AH}) \quad (2)$$

The first term represents the modified coulomb interaction and the last one the overlap repulsive interactions. Z, A, λ, P, b, m and N are the constants of potentials. The repulsive potential in equation (2) has also been adopted by the earlier workers^{7,8} from where it is evident that the value of m has been chosen arbitrarily and the value of N kept as variable for getting the optimal agreement between the calculated and experimental values.

In the present work, we assume N to account for the uncounted contributions in the repulsive potential. As the repulsive potential depends upon the electronic environment, the constants m and N may, however, be considered as the dependent of electronic environment which arises from the valence electrons. According to valence bond theory, the major contributions in the bond formation in diatomic molecules (ionic or covalent) come from the valence electrons. Keeping in view these facts, m and N may be correlated with valence electrons. In our earlier paper⁹, we expressed them as

$$m = 2 \text{ and } N = \frac{m(V_1^2 + V_2^2)^{1/2}}{(V_1 + V_2)} + 0.085 \left(\frac{V_2}{V_1} \right) \quad (3)$$

when both atom (like or unlike) have ns or $ns np$ -valence state and

$$m = 2 \text{ and } N = \frac{m(V_1^2 + V_2^2)^{1/2}}{(V_1 + V_2)} - 0.035 \left(\frac{V_2}{V_1} \right) \quad (4)$$

when one atom ns -valence state and another has $ns np$ -valence state. V_1 is the number of valence electrons associated with the outermost s or p orbitals in the first atom and V_2 is the number of valence electrons of other atom having the valence state configurations like $ns^1, ns^2, ns^2 np^x$ (x varies from 1 to 5). For heavy metal halides, N comes

out to be approximately 1.5. The specific form of the potential energy function which has been found to be reasonable is achieved for $m=2$ and $N=3/2$ in the general form given in equation (2). The empirical relations (3 and 4) also explain the type of bonding in diatomic molecules. For example, there exists $s-p$ type of bonding in the halides of Cu and Ag and $p-p$ type of bonding in the halides of Ga, In and Tl.

Method of analysis :

The potential parameters are determined phenomenologically using the conditions,

$$(dU/dr)_{r=r_0} = 0 \tag{5}$$

$$(d^2U/dr^2)_{r=r_0} = k_e \tag{6}$$

and $U(r_0) = -D_i \tag{7}$

where r_0 is the equilibrium internuclear separation, $U(r_0)$ is the total potential energy, k_e is the force constant and D_i is the experimental value of binding energy. Finally, the potential parameters are expressed as follows.

Hellmann potential :

$$Z^2 = \frac{r_0 U}{e^2} \left(\frac{U}{k_e r_0^2} - 1 \right) \tag{8}$$

$$A r_0^{-1} \exp(-\lambda r_0) = -\frac{Z^2 e^2}{r_0 (\lambda r_0 + 1)} \tag{9}$$

$$\lambda r_0 = -\left(\frac{k_e r_0^2}{U} \right) \tag{10}$$

AH potential :

$$Z^2 = -\frac{r_0 U (3x+4)}{e^2 (3x+2)} \tag{11}$$

$$P r_0^{-2} \exp(-b r_0^{3/2}) = -\frac{2U}{(3x+2)} \tag{12}$$

$$x = \frac{-(2K_e r_0^2 + 3U) - (4K_e^2 r_0^4 - 4K_e r_0^2 U - 23U^2)^{1/2}}{6U} \tag{13}$$

where $x = b r_0^{3/2}$, and these parameters are listed in Table 1. The values of D_i , α_e and $w_e x_e$ are calculated using the relations cited in reference 1 and the calculated values are compared with the corresponding experimental data¹⁰ in Table 2. The experimental data of D_i is not available in the literature and hence we have estimated it. All the input data are taken from Huber and Herzberg¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

It is evident from Table 2 that the values of D_i calculated with $Z=1$ are not in complete agreement with the experimental values showing the existence of considerable amount of polarisation and covalent effects. The calculated values of α_e and $w_e x_e$ with $Z=1$ are too high and hence for the sake of brevity, these are not reported. With the inclusion of effective charge parameter, the agreement between theoretical and experimental values is significantly improved. The results may further be improved provided the necessary data are available to take into account the contributions of polarisation and Van der Waals energies. Our P.E. function gives better results than the Hellmann potential although Hellmann potential is quantum mechanically based.

The P.E. curves for AH potential may be written as

$$U = \frac{Z^2 e^2}{r} \left[-1 + \frac{2e^{-b(r^{3/2} - r_0^{3/2})} r_0}{3b r_0^{3/2} + 4} \frac{r_0}{r} \right] \tag{14}$$

The P.E. curves for AgF, CuF and TlF are obtained with and without the inclusion of effective charge parameter (Fig. 1). The P.E. curves pass through minima at the equilibrium value of r_0 as expected, where the two atoms are said to be bonded together and the attractive and repulsive forces are equal. Hence the system is expected to be stable at $r=r_0$. The curves show that when the separation between the nuclei is sufficiently large, i.e. $r \rightarrow \infty$, the P.E.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF INPUT DATA : INTERNUCLEAR SEPARATION (r_0 Å), MOLECULAR FORCE CONSTANT (k_e , 10^5 dyne cm^{-1}) AND CALCULATED VALUES OF POTENTIAL PARAMETERS AND IONIC CHARACTER (I.C.)

Molecule	r_0	k_e	I.C. eq. (15)	AH		Hellmann	
				Z	$\lambda r_0^{3/2}$	Z	r_0
AgF	1.989 2	2.523 84	0.49	1.08	4.990 97	1.08	8.163 21
AgCl	2.280 8	1.845 00	0.11	1.11	5.255 08	1.11	8.551 49
AgBr	2.393 1	1.690 65	0.17	1.14	5.215 70	1.12	8.493 55
AgI	2.544 6	1.468 69	0.11	1.16	5.299 70	1.17	8.617 18
CuF	1.744 9	3.357 53	0.49	1.08	4.530 07	1.08	7.487 44
CuCl	2.051 2	2.326 25	0.11	1.12	4.719 41	1.12	7.764 78
CuBr	2.173 4	2.059 07	0.17	1.13	4.873 68	1.14	7.991 02
GaF	1.774 4	3.421 71	0.58	1.07	4.920 95	1.07	8.060 39
GaCl	2.201 7	1.837 22	0.17	1.10	4.740 64	1.10	7.809 10
GaBr	2.352 5	1.527 87	0.24	1.11	4.765 83	1.11	7.532 83
GaI	2.574 7	1.243 62	0.17	1.11	5.109 26	1.11	8.337 04
InF	1.985 4	2.772 88	0.55	1.06	5.711 58	1.06	9.224 10
InCl	2.401 2	1.602 87	0.15	1.09	5.547 73	1.09	8.982 52
InBr	2.543 1	1.376 23	0.22	1.10	5.531 66	1.10	8.958 84
InI	2.753 6	1.122 45	0.15	1.12	5.546 54	1.12	8.980 76
TlF	2.084 4	2.117 62	0.52	1.07	4.975 78	1.07	8.140 92
TlCl	2.484 8	1.285 39	0.13	1.09	4.926 91	1.09	8.069 17
TlBr	2.618 2	1.144 55	0.20	1.10	5.019 00	1.10	8.204 39
TlI	2.813 6	0.942 81	0.13	1.10	5.113 74	1.10	8.343 61

*Ground state.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF BINDING ENERGY (D_1), ROTATION-VIBRATION COUPLING CONSTANT (α_e) AND VIBRATIONAL ANHARMONICITY CONSTANT ($we\alpha_e$)

Molecule	D_1 (kJ mol ⁻¹)			$\alpha_e(10^{-4}$ cm ⁻¹)			$we\alpha_e$ (cm ⁻¹)		
	Expt.*	AH	Hellmann	Expt.	AH	Hellmann	Expt.	AH	Hellmann
AgF	732.3	635.4	633.4	19.206	21.494	22.448	2.593	3.106	3.202
AgCl	675.9	557.2	555.7	5.955	7.217	7.531	1.170	1.153	1.584
AgBr	686.5	533.4	532.0	2.282	2.641	2.757	0.679	0.785	0.809
AgI	664.6	503.2	502.0	1.414	1.610	1.680	0.445	0.567	0.584
CuF	822.2	716.1	713.5	32.298	33.104	34.619	3.950	3.918	4.046
CuCl	759.1	615.3	613.5	9.964	11.118	11.621	1.580	1.917	1.979
CuBr	733.0	583.2	584.1	4.521	5.048	5.274	0.960	1.155	1.191
GaF	804.9	708.4	706.1	28.642	32.057	33.488	3.200	4.127	4.255
GaCl	686.8	572.2	570.4	7.936	9.192	9.607	1.200	1.644	1.696
GaBr	650.1	536.1	534.5	3.207	3.847	3.989	0.810	0.910	0.930
GaI	595.5	492.5	491.1	1.890	2.390	2.495	0.500	0.686	0.707
InF	713.6	639.7	637.9	18.797	22.761	23.713	2.640	3.671	3.774
InCl	619.6	529.9	528.4	5.178	6.457	6.731	1.010	1.467	1.509
InBr	598.3	501.1	499.7	1.862	2.343	2.443	0.650	0.735	0.756
InI	570.7	468.9	462.9	1.041	1.323	1.378	0.400	0.496	0.510
TlF	680.6	603.3	601.3	15.038	16.263	16.986	2.300	2.599	2.679
TlCl	592.3	507.2	505.6	3.979	4.549	4.751	0.818	1.050	1.083
TlBr	575.9	483.0	481.6	1.275	1.469	1.534	0.390	0.499	0.514
TlI	538.7	450.3	448.9	0.664	0.786	0.821	—	0.383	0.394
Av. % Dev.		16.3	16.6		16.7	21.7		24.5	27.2

*Estimated from the relation $D_1 = D_e + I - E$, where D_e is the dissociation energy¹⁰, I the ionisation potential and E the electron affinity; I and E are taken from Pauling¹³.

Fig. 1. Potential energy curves for AgF, TlF and CuF molecules. Purely electrostatic effects: (—○) [Ag⁺F⁻], (—□) [Tl⁺F⁻], (—△) [Cu⁺F⁻]; polarisation and covalent effects: (---○) [Ag^{δ+}-F^{δ-}], (---□) [Tl^{δ+}-F^{δ-}], (---△) [Cu^{δ+}-F^{δ-}].

must approach an asymptote. This indicates a limiting value known as dissociation energy, D_0 ,

at which the molecules dissociate into atoms. Thus, our P.E. function satisfies the Varshni criteria¹¹.

The ionic character (I.C.) of bond in heavy metal halides can be calculated using the expression¹² which is an improved formula of Pauling¹³,

$$\text{I.C.} = 0.16(X_A - X_B) + 0.035(X_A - X_B)^2 \quad (15)$$

where X_A and X_B are the electronegativities taken from Pauling¹³.

To sum up, we may say that heavy metal halide molecules possess (i) ionic bonding (M^+X^-) as well as (ii) polarised covalent bonding ($M^{\delta+}-X^{\delta-}$) which are also supported by well-known Fajan's rules for polarisation.

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